

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMING STUDENTS' ENGLISH LANGUAGE SKILLS

¹Ibraimov Xolboy Ibragimovich, ²Begmatov Mansur Adgarovich

¹Director of the Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozhi, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

²Researcher, Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after T.N.Kori Niyozhi

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Abstract. *This article discusses the theoretical foundations for developing students' English language skills. In particular, the role of conceptualization in the process of developing English language skills is considered, as well as methods and techniques that can be used to develop these skills.*

Keywords: *english language, theory, formation, skills, conceptualization, method, communication, cognitive abilities.*

Introduction. The modern world is becoming increasingly global, and the position of the English language plays an important role in this process. Language provides the function of communication between people from different countries and cultures, allowing you to study, work, live and travel abroad. In this regard, developing students' English language skills is of paramount importance. This knowledge of the English language is not only the key to good life prospects, it is also considered by many scientists in the field as a determining factor in the global competitiveness of an individual and a country. Of the main tasks in developing English language skills in development, four main competencies are noted: reading, writing, speaking and listening. Each of these competencies has its own characteristics and requires the use of appropriate teaching methods.

Language proficiency is the ability to use language to communicate. Language skills include grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, speech and writing. Building language skills is a process that involves learning the language, practicing, and accepting feedback.

Depending on the goal from the point of view of the theoretical basis, the development of English language skills in a student may include:

1. Learning Phonetics and Pronunciation - Students' ability to pronounce sounds and words correctly to understand their speech concepts and communicate.

2. Development of speech comprehension skills is the ability of students to understand speech in various contexts, such as conversations, lectures, etc.

3. Development of reading skills - students' skills to understand and study without difficulty.

4. Development of writing skills - literate, competent and effective writing skills in students.

5. Development of grammar and vocabulary skills - the ability of students to use correct grammar and vocabulary when communicating in English.

6. Development of communication skills is the ability of students to communicate effectively in various contexts.

7. Developing cultural competence skills is the skill by which students perceive differences in the concept of culture and use them in English-language communication.

Building English language skills is an important task for educational institutions and society as a whole.

Basic concepts and definitions: this part of the article contains definitions of basic concepts related to the subject of the study, such as “English language skills”, “skill formation”, “theoretical foundations”.

Knowledge of English is the ability to speak, read, write and understand English. These skills can be developed in a variety of ways such as grammar, vocabulary, listening and speaking practice. However, speaking English can be an important skill for work, study or travel.

Skill building is the process of developing English language. This process includes studying English at school or higher education institutions, self-studying the language, participating in courses and trainings, as well as practical use of the language in real life situations. The formation of English language skills is based on theoretical foundations that determine the principles of organizing the educational process. One of the main theoretical concepts is the communicative approach, which understands the active use of language in real communicative situations.

Theoretical framework is the basis of the theory associated with learning English. These basics include grammar, vocabulary, phonics and practical skills. The theoretical framework can be used to develop curricula, courses, and techniques to help students develop English language skills.

Conceptualization is the process of developing an understanding and understanding of language. It includes not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also the ability to understand and use language in practice.

Methods for developing English language skills: This part of the article presents various teaching methods that can be used to develop English language skills, such as the project method, game situation method, business game method, etc. There are many methods and techniques that can be used to develop English language skills. In this article we will look at some of them.

1. **Use of interactive teaching methods:** Interactive teaching methods such as games, role plays, discussions, etc. can be very effective in building English language skills. They allow students to use the language in practice, and also develop communication and social adaptation skills.

2. **Developing Reading and Writing Skills:** Reading and writing skills are important components of English language proficiency. Various methods can be used to develop them, such as reading books and articles in English, writing essays and papers, and holding discussions and debates in English.

3. **Use of technology:** Modern technologies such as online courses, mobile applications and interactive textbooks can be very helpful in building English language skills. They allow students to learn a language anywhere, anytime, and provide access to a wide range of materials and exercises.

4. **Developing listening and speaking skills:** Listening and speaking skills are key to mastering the English language. Various methods can be used to develop them, such as listening to audio recordings and videos in English, holding discussions and conversations with native speakers, and conducting role-playing games and debates in English. Factors influencing the

development of English language skills: In this part of the article, we can discuss various factors that can influence the development of English language skills, such as student motivation, level of linguistic competence, socio-cultural context, etc.

There are many factors that influence the development of English language skills. Some of them:

1. *Student motivation.* The more motivation and interest a student has in learning English, the more successful his or her learning process will be.

2. *Quality of teaching.* An experienced and qualified teacher can significantly improve the effectiveness of the learning process.

3. *Learning Environment or Cultural Context:* Students who are exposed to an environment where English is used as the primary language of communication have greater opportunities to develop language skills.

4. *Regularity of classes,* self-discipline and constant practice help to consolidate acquired knowledge and develop English language skills.

5. *The use of various teaching methods* and techniques helps students better understand the material and develop English language skills.

6. *Individual characteristics.* The student has his own individual characteristics, which can affect the learning process and the development of English language skills. For example, level of intelligence, memory, learning abilities, etc.

Conclusion. In the final part of the article, you can summarize the results of the study and draw conclusions about what theoretical foundations and methods of developing English language skills can be most effective for modern education. Building English language skills is a complex process that requires not only knowledge of grammar and vocabulary, but also the development of skills to understand and use the language in practice. Conceptualization plays an important role in this process by enabling students to understand and use language in practice. Various methods and techniques can be used to develop English language skills, such as interactive teaching methods, development of reading and writing skills, use of technology, and development of listening and speaking skills.

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